

(CASE REPORT)

Anesthesia in the elderly with colon cancer and postoperative outcome

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Abstract

Colorectal surgery is commonly performed for colorectal cancer but morbidity and mortality remain high and vary among surgical centers. Two elderly patients with Colorectal Cancer and a history of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease underwent epidural anesthesia plus general anesthesia for colectomy surgery. In addition, Bridium was used as an inhibitor of muscle relaxation to better awaken them. The aim of the study was to evaluate the postoperative outcome of elderly patients with colorectal cancer and session disease Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, when they undergo anesthesia to perform a major surgery such as colectomy. The combination of epidural and general anesthesia showed encouraging results in the postoperative outcome of these patients and Bridium's effect on winning was significant.

Keywords: Anesthesia; Cancer; COPD; Elderly; Surgery

1. Introduction

Colorectal surgery for cancer, diverticular, or inflammatory diseases is a high-risk surgery. Other indications for CR surgery include ischemic colitis, iatrogenic perforation or injury, and volvulus. Perioperative factors affecting colon blood flow and oxygenation, suppression of stress response, optimal fluid therapy, and multimodal pain management are essential for the successful anesthetic management and a favorable perioperative outcome. The goals of perioperative anesthetic management for surgical patients are minimizing stress and immune responses, maintaining systemic and colonic blood flow and oxygenation, meticulous fluid and electrolyte therapy, multimodal analgesia, and prevention of postoperative gut dysfunction. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a common disease in elderly patients. Although most COPD patients tolerate tracheal intubation under "smooth" anesthetic induction without serious adverse effects, regional anesthetic blockade and application of laryngeal masks or non-invasive positive pressure ventilation should be considered whenever possible, in order to provide optimal pain control and to prevent upper airway injuries as well as lung baro-volutrauma. Minimally-invasive procedures and modern multimodal analgesic regimen are helpful to minimize the surgical stress response, to speed up the physiological recovery process and to shorten the hospital stay. Reflex-induced bronchoconstriction and hyperdynamic inflation during mechanical ventilation could be prevented by using bronchodilating volatile anesthetics and adjusting the ventilatory settings with long expiration times. Intraoperatively, the depth of anesthesia, the circulatory volume and neuromuscular blockade should be assessed with modern physiological monitoring tools to titrate the administration of anesthetic agents, fluids and myorelaxant drugs [1-26].

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2. Case Study

Two patients aged 82 and 86 years, respectively, with a body weight of 70 kg and 75 kg, underwent colectomy with surgical etiology of colon cancer and concomitant chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with a relatively good response to bronchodilation. In both patients, an epidural catheter was placed at the lumbar level 2 - lumbar 3, with a test dose of 3 ml Lidocaine 2%, under continuous monitoring with NBP, ECG, SpO₂. Introduction to anesthesia was performed with 1 mg Dormicum, Fentanyl 0.1 mg, Propofol 150 mg and Esmeron 80 mg and ligated after inhalation into Drager respirators using the Volune Control ventilation model (Tidal Volume: 420 ml, Frequency: 16, PEEP: 5). After vital signs were checked, 5 ml Naropain 0.75% was given through the epidural catheter. Maintenance of anesthesia was done with Sevoflurane 2.5% and O₂ / Air: 50/50%. After the start of the operation the patients were hydrated by slow infusion of 1Lt Plasmalite and epidurally given 10 ml Naropaine 0.375% plus 2 mg Morphine. The duration of the surgery was about two hours. Two hours after the start of the surgery, a Baxter continuous infusion pump, with an infusion rate of 5 ml / h, Naropaine 2%, was connected to the epidural catheter. The epidural infusion pump was maintained postoperatively.

After the completion of the surgery, the Sevoflurane faucet was closed and an O₂ / N₂O: 50/50% mixture was placed with a Pressure Control ventilation model. When the minimal alveolar concentration of Sevofluran dropped to 0.4, pure oxygen was given at a flow rate of 12 Lt and Bridium 300 mg at a slow infusion. The intubation was performed in full vigilance, after they had regained sufficient respiratory range. They were taken to the post-operative monitoring room of their vital signs, with a simple oxygen mask at 2 Lt for half an hour.

3. Management and Outcome

Rapid onset of epidural anesthesia with 3 ml test dose Lidocaine and 5 ml Naropaine 0.75% reduces the need for large doses of opioids. Then the second infusion of a lower concentration of Naropaine 0.375% and 2 mg Morfine creates a satisfactory level of analgesia. Thus epidural anesthesia reduces the required doses of opioids, offering satisfactory analgesia and helping to win these patients. In addition, Bridium for more effective reversal of muscle relaxation is necessary in elderly patients when they undergo major surgeries such as colectomy and especially when they have concomitant diseases such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Sevoflurane is a good choice for respiratory patients as it does not irritate their respiratory system. Plasmalite was used to avoid sympatholysis. The continuous anesthetic pump in the epidural maintains a constant level of analgesia and helps in the better postoperative outcome of these patients.

4. Discussion

Elderly exiled patients are more difficult to release from the ventilator. The possibility of inability to release the ventilator increases when undergoing major surgery and especially abdominal surgery with large incisions as in a colectomy. When they present with concomitant diseases, very common in elderly patients and especially with respiratory diseases, such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, then the probability of hospitalization in the ICU and the failure of a good postoperative outcome of these patients greatly increases. The combination of epidural - general anesthesia and the use of Bridium in the awakening contributes to the faster release from the ventilator and the better postoperative course.

5. Conclusion

Epidural anesthesia plus general anesthesia, the use of Bridium in winning and the adequate analgesic action offered by the epidural local anesthetic infusion pump, reduce or eliminate ICU hospitalization days in elderly patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and better obstructive pulmonary disease.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

General Hospital of Larisa.

Statement of informed consent

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report. A copy of the written consent is available.

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